

An aerial photograph of Delhi, India, showing a dense urban landscape with numerous buildings and a prominent minaret in the foreground. The sky is hazy, suggesting air pollution. The minaret is a tall, slender structure with a domed top and a smaller dome at the base. The city below is a mix of old and new buildings, with a mix of colors and textures. The overall scene is a mix of urban density and historical architecture.

Delhi's Air: What People Think and Want

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Executive Summary

Delhi's Air: What People Think and Want

Air pollution in Delhi is among the most severe globally, with $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} levels far exceeding World Health Organization guidelines. Yet, less is known about how people in Delhi perceive this challenge, who they believe should take responsibility, and which solutions they support. We conducted an online survey of 3,406 respondents in early 2025 to better understand public perceptions of air pollution and preferences for air quality policies.

Air pollution is a top public concern: Air pollution ranks as the most important problem facing Delhi, chosen more often than public safety, clean water access, and healthcare quality. **An overwhelming 87% of respondents reported being either “very” or “extremely” concerned.** Concern is widespread across demographic groups, although it is particularly high among older and more highly educated respondents. These findings signal that air pollution is a deeply salient issue in people's lives.

Shared responsibility, but mixed views on effort: In Delhi, **air pollution mitigation is widely seen as a shared responsibility.** The local government (25%) and citizens (24%) were most frequently identified as responsible, followed by the national government (20%) and businesses (17%). However, views on actual effort are sharply divided: while 39–45% believe these actors are doing too little, 40–42% say they are doing too much. **This split reveals a disconnect between who is seen as responsible and how their performance is perceived.** While there is consensus on who should act, opinions diverge on how well they perform, potentially complicating efforts to build broad public support for stronger measures.

Strong alignment between perception and policy priorities: Respondents largely agree that transportation, industry, and waste burning are the primary sources of air pollution, and they want government action focused on these areas.

Widespread support for air pollution policies: Support for action is consistently high across all six proposed measures. The most popular are increased fines for waste burning (87%), better public information (85%), and stricter industry regulations (84%). Even more intrusive or costly policies, such as banning older vehicles (82%), expanding household electrification (75%), and investing in public transport despite higher fares (68%), receive strong majority backing. **Support remains high across socio-demographic groups,** with only modest variation by age and education.

Key take-aways: Delhi respondents are highly concerned about air pollution and widely support a range of interventions to address it. Despite divergence in perceptions of how much different actors are doing, the overall message is clear: people want decisive, multisectoral action.

Based upon these findings, we identify several recommendations for policymakers and air pollution stakeholders in Delhi

1. Implementing high-support policies such as fines for waste burning, health information campaigns, and stricter industry regulation.
2. Expanding support for less popular but effective policies, like public transportation investment, through fairness-enhancing mechanisms such as subsidies or exemptions.
3. Building on strong public demand to advance cleaner air policies, leveraging Delhi's comparatively high receptiveness to even costlier interventions.

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Delhi: City Overview

In 2022 and 2023, PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels fluctuated in Delhi¹, peaking during the Northern Hemisphere's winter. Both pollutants consistently surpassed the World Health Organization's guidelines, with annual averages of 51.4 µg/m³ for PM₁₀ and 73.6 µg/m³ for PM_{2.5} – around 6 and 15 times higher than recommended limits, respectively.

Monthly PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} Levels, 2021-2023, Delhi

Delhi

\$11,300 GDP per Capita

11,300/km² Population Density

India

0.29 Liberal Democracy V-Dem Index

0.26 Gini Coefficient

Delhi, India's capital, has high population density² and a GDP per capita of \$11,300³. India is considered moderately unequal in economic terms (Gini: 0.33)⁴, and classified as an electoral autocracy, scoring 0.29 on the Liberal Democracy Index⁵.

In India, Air Pollution Is Responsible for⁶:

41%
of stroke deaths

20%
of diabetes deaths

40%
of ischemic heart disease deaths

33%
of neonatal deaths

39%
of lower-respiratory infection deaths

70%
of COPD deaths

33%
of lung cancer deaths

About 1.9 million Indians are estimated die prematurely due to air pollution each year⁷, with children under five accounting for about 43% of these fatalities in 2021⁸.

2025 Survey in Delhi

This report contains data from a survey of Delhi residents, fielded between February and March 2025. For this survey, an online-based sample (n=3,406) was recruited via partnership with a commercial online panel provider (Dynata).

To achieve representativeness of the city population with respect to age (18-59 years) and gender, quota-based sampling methods were used.

Survey quality was ensured through two attention checks and a minimum completion time based on the soft launch median; respondents who failed two or more of these checks were excluded from the final sample.

In total, the study surveyed 3,406 participants. The sample consisted of 50% women and 50% men. The largest age group represented was 18-29 years, followed by the 30-39 and 40-49 age groups.

In terms of educational attainment, the most common ones were master's degree, bachelor's degree and advanced diploma. Respondents were drawn from across the city, with the highest concentration coming from Old and New Delhi (see map above).

Education Level Distribution

Age Level Distribution

Salience of and Concern About Air Pollution

Salience of Air Pollution

In the first survey item, respondents were asked to select the three most important issues from a list of 10 challenges faced in Delhi. Air pollution was chosen most often, accounting for 24% of all responses, followed by public safety (14%), access to clean water (11%), and healthcare quality (10%).

Ranking of Most Important Problems in Delhi:

- **1. Air Pollution**
- **2. Public Safety**
- **3. Access to Clean Water**
- **4. Quality of Healthcare**
- **5. Government Corruption**
- **6. Problems With Road Infrastructure**
- **7. Personal Economic Situation**
- **8. Inequality and Discrimination**
- **9. Affordability of Housing**
- **10. Reliable and Affordable Access to Electricity**

Concern About Air Pollution

In general, an overwhelming majority of respondents (87%) were either “very” (36%) or “extremely” (51%) concerned about air pollution. Another 11% were “somewhat concerned”, while only 1% said they were “not at all concerned.”

Concern levels were similar across genders, with some differences found between different age groups and levels of education. For instance, older respondents (aged 50-59) were more likely to be extremely concerned (65%) – a sentiment shared much less by those aged 18-29 (43%). While less educated respondents were more likely to be not concerned at all (7%), they were also substantially less likely to be extremely concerned (33%). This contrasts with well-educated respondents, who were more likely to express extreme concern (55%).

These findings reveal strong and widespread concern about air pollution, with noticeable socio-demographic differences in degree.

Levels of Concern About Air Pollution by Socio-Demographics

Sources of Air Pollution

We presented respondents in Delhi with a list of 8 potential sources of air pollution, and we asked them to select the three sources they think cause most pollution. Transportation and industry were seen as top contributors, followed by waste burning, construction, and power plants.

When compared to a scientific assessment of air pollution sources in India⁷, some of the sources overlap, such as industry (2), power plants (3) and construction (4). Nonetheless, other substantial sources of air pollution were less often identified by respondents, such as heating and cooking (1) and agriculture (5).

This juxtaposition reveals a certain gap between public perception and scientific assessments of air pollution sources. Despite the identification of many major contributors by respondents, other important sources like household heating and cooking or agriculture go unnoticed by the public. This gap also highlights the potential for targeted communication campaigns to improve localised knowledge about the sources of air pollution - a crucial element in fostering individual behaviour change and support for policies that address these sources.

Perceptions of Sources vs. Prioritisation of Action for Air Pollution

The study then compared respondents' perceptions of major air pollution sources with the sources they prioritised for government action. On the left, we show the sources perceived to contribute most to air pollution, and on the right, the sources respondents most want targeted by policy. This allows for a direct comparison of the two relative rankings.

Perceptions of Sources vs. Prioritisation of Action for Air Pollution

Overall, perceptions and priorities align closely. For example, 21% identify industry as a major source and equally want the government to prioritise it. The findings suggest that citizens want the government to focus on transportation, industry, and waste burning.

Air Pollution Reduction Responsibilities

Who Is Responsible for Air Pollution Reduction?

Air Pollution Reduction

We also asked respondents who they thought was most responsible for reducing air pollution, allowing up to three choices.

Local government (25%) and citizens (24%) were most frequently selected, suggesting that responsibility is placed more at the local and community level. However, the national government (20%) and businesses (17%) were also commonly cited, indicating a shared sense of responsibility across society.

In contrast, experts (10%) and international organisations (3%) were less frequently seen as key actors responsible for addressing air pollution.

How Much Are Actors Doing to Reduce Air Pollution?

Action on Air Pollution Reduction

In addition, we asked respondents how much effort local government, businesses, and citizens are making to lower air pollution. Here, responses reveal deep divisions regarding how much these three actors are doing.

Between 39% and 45% of respondents perceive these actors to be doing not enough or too little, while 40-42% of respondents believe they are doing too much or far too much. The remaining share (13-19%) says efforts by the different actors are just right.

Citizens were slightly more likely to be seen as doing the right amount (19%), too much or far too much (42%). Businesses, by contrast, were more often viewed as falling short – 45% said they were doing too little or not enough.

Overall, the results suggest that the public views reducing air pollution as a common task to be addressed by government, businesses and citizens alike. Yet, public opinion is polarised regarding the current efforts of these actors to reduce air pollution, with nearly equal proportions believing each group is doing either too much or too little.

Public Demand for Air Pollution Policies

Public Demand for Air Pollution Policies

To understand public preferences for government actions on air pollution, we asked respondents to evaluate six different potential policies. These ranged from bans and fines, such as prohibiting older vehicles or penalising waste burning, to low-cost measures like more information about air pollution's health impacts. Other policies combined regulation with costs, including increased household electrification, expanded public transportation, and industry regulation.

Support for these policies was high across the board. A majority favoured or strongly favoured each policy. Increased fines on waste burning receive the highest support (87%), followed by the policy of providing more information (85%), stricter industry regulation (84%), banning old vehicles (82%), increased household electrification (75%), and the expansion of public transportation (68%). Opposition to all policies was very low, ranging from 7% of respondents opposing waste burning fines and information campaigns to 19% of respondents disliking the expansion of public transport.

This implies that the public in Delhi is highly supportive of measures that target polluters and raise awareness. Even policies involving behavioural restrictions or direct costs, such as increased ticket prices for the expansion of public transportation, enjoy substantial support.

Support for Regulating Industry by Socio-Demographics

Preferences vary more by respondents' level of education. Those with moderate or low education express slightly less support (78% and 76%), with the latter also showing somewhat higher opposition (21% compared to 7% for respondents with high education).

Still, strong majorities across all groups favour more rigorous industry regulation, indicating broad public demand for this policy.

Regulations on Industry

How do individual policy preferences vary by socio-demographic characteristics?

Support for regulating industries – even if it leads to higher product prices – remains high (84%) and is largely consistent across gender and age groups. However, respondents aged 18-29 tend to favour the policy slightly less (79%).

Electricity Access

Next, we examine public support for increasing household access to electricity, even if it results in higher electricity prices. A solid majority (75%) supports this policy, with slight variation across age groupings.

Older respondents (50–59) are the most supportive (80%) and least opposed (9%). They are also more committed in their degree of support, with 47% strongly in favour, compared to 23% among 18–29-year-olds.

Support for Expanding Electricity Access by Socio-Demographics

Respondents in the youngest age group indicate comparatively lower support (69%) and slightly stronger opposition (16%).

Regarding education, support is slightly lower (66%) and opposition slightly higher (17%) among those with moderate educational attainment.

Overall, despite its potential direct cost, the electrification policy enjoys broad support – especially among older respondents – with only minor drop-offs across demographic groups.

Public Transportation

We then focus on socio-demographic variation in support for more public transportation, funded through higher ticket prices. While broadly supported across all of the respondents (68%), there is a slight differences based upon age groupings and educational attainment.

Support is marginally lower among respondents aged 18-29 (62%) and opposition is higher (24%), compared to other age groups. This may reflect recent discussions on metro passes in Delhi, with students protesting in favour of concessional tickets⁹.

Similarly, those with moderate education are also slightly less supportive (59%). Additionally, both respondents with moderate and low education oppose the policy more frequently (24% and 27%, respectively).

Despite these variations, majorities across all socio-demographic groups favour the policy, though small pockets of opposition remain.

Support for Expanding Public Transportation by Socio-Demographics

Ban on Old Vehicles

Finally, we assess attitudes toward banning older vehicles, broken down by socio-demographic characteristics. Overall, the policy is met with solid public support, with 82% in favour and 10% opposed.

Minor differences in support show up by age groups and levels of education. Support is slightly lower among younger respondents (18-29), at 77%, and among those with medium or low education.

Support for Banning Old Vehicles by Socio-Demographics

This may echo sentiments around a recent Supreme Court-backed ban on old vehicles, which was considered unjust to lower- and middle-income households by protesters¹⁰. Still, around three-quarters of these groups support the policy.

In sum, banning older vehicles enjoys substantial backing across all socio-demographic segments.

Air Pollution Policy Support Across Middle-Income Cities

We also compared support for air pollution policies in Delhi with three major middle-income cities: Accra (Ghana), Jakarta (Indonesia), and Johannesburg (South Africa).

Comparison of Air Pollution Policy Support in Middle-Income Cities

Overall, support in Delhi is consistently higher than in the other cities. Policies like fines for waste burning (87%), providing more information (85%), and stricter industry regulations (84%) enjoy especially strong backing, exceeding levels seen in Accra, Johannesburg, and Jakarta.

Even more contentious measures – such as banning old vehicles – are well supported in Delhi (82%), compared to 65% in Accra, 67% in Jakarta, and 37% in Johannesburg. Although bans tend to elicit more resistance due to personal costs, Delhi respondents appear highly receptive, possibly due to greater exposure to vehicle emissions and familiarity with past policy efforts.

Support is somewhat lower for expanding electricity access (72%) and public transportation investment (68%), yet still significantly higher than in the comparison cities.

These results show that Delhi consistently ranks among the most supportive cities for air pollution policies. High levels of public backing, even for costlier measures, suggest favourable conditions for policy adoption. At the same time, variation across cities shows that policy preferences are shaped by local context, underscoring the need to tailor solutions to specific urban settings and public priorities.

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